

MICROMECHANICS ANALYSIS OF FIBRE FRAGMENTATION TEST

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ABSTRACT

A micromechanics model has been developed of the stress transfer for the fibre fragmentation test, taking into account both the bonded and debonded regions. Depending on the relative magnitudes of the interfacial bond strength and the fibre strength for given elastic constants and geometric factors, three distinct interfaces (i.e. full bonding, partial debonding and full frictional bonding) are identified and the conditions necessary to satisfy each interface quantitatively evaluated. The mean fibre fragment length is predicted as a function of applied strain using a model composite of carbon fibre-epoxy matrix.

Key Words: fibre Fragmentation; micromechanics Analysis; interface; debonding.

1 INTRODUCTION

The recognition of the important role of fibre-matrix interface properties in controlling the mechanical/structural performance of fibre composites has directed a great deal of research endeavour in both experiments and theoretical analyses [1,2]. The fibre fragmentation test is one of the most popular among the various test methods to characterise the interface properties using single fibre composites. In this test, the fibre breaks into increasingly smaller lengths with increasing applied load until the average fibre length reaches the critical value $2L_c$. Assuming that the interface is completely debonded or the surrounding matrix is yielded, the apparent shear strength, τ_a , at the interface region is estimated from the knowledge of tensile strength, σ_{TS} , and diameter, d , of the fibre based on the simple relation [3]:

$$2L_c = \sigma_{TS} d / 2 \tau_a \quad (1)$$

Contrary to the uniform interface shear stress as assumed for half the fibre length in the above equation, a widely accepting view in recent years [4,5] proposed for the correct interpretation of experimental data is that there are bonded and debonded regions present simultaneously at the fibre-matrix interface. As a result, the apparent interface shear strength,

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τ_a , can only be regarded as an average value for the adhesive bond and frictional properties at the respective interfaces.

In the present paper, an improved micromechanics analysis is presented of the fibre fragmentation test based on the shear strength criterion for the interfacial debonding. Depending on the interface properties and the fibre tensile strength for given elastic constants of the composite constituents, three distinct interface situations are identified which include complete bonding, partial debonding and complete frictional bonding, and the conditions required to satisfy each interface are obtained. Therefore, solutions are derived for the stress distributions in the constituents, the external stress required for debonding or fibre fragmentation, and the mean fibre fragmentation length for the three different interface conditions. Treating the partially debonded interface as the most general case, a parametric study is performed for a model composite of a carbon fibre in an epoxy matrix.

Figure 1. A schematic illustration of the partially debonded fibre in the fibre fragmentation model.

2 ANALYSIS

2.1 Solutions for the Stress Components

For the shear-lag model in cylindrical coordinate (r, θ, z) which is symmetric about the fibre axis and the mid-plane at $z = 0$ as shown in Figure 1, a single fibre (of total length $2L$ with a debonded length ℓ at its both ends) is embedded at the centre of a coaxial cylindrical shell of matrix material. When a tensile stress, σ , is applied to the matrix at the remote ends, stress is transferred to the fibre across the interface such that the stress distributions in the fibre and interfaces in the bonded region $(-L-\ell) \leq z \leq (L-\ell)$ are given by [6]:

$$\sigma_f^z(z) = \left(\frac{1 + \gamma}{\alpha + \gamma} \right) \left\{ 1 - \frac{\cosh(\beta z)}{\cosh[\beta(L-\ell)]} \right\} \sigma + \frac{\cosh(\beta z)}{\cosh[\beta(L-\ell)]} \sigma_\ell \quad (2)$$

$$\tau_i^{rz}(z) = \left(\frac{a\beta}{2} \right) \left\{ \left(\frac{1 + \gamma}{\alpha + \gamma} \right) \sigma - \sigma_\ell \right\} \frac{\sinh(\beta z)}{\cosh[\beta(L-\ell)]} \quad (3)$$

where

$$\beta^2 = \frac{(b^2 - a^2) (1 + \alpha/\gamma)}{(1 + \gamma) [b^4 \ln(b/a) - (b^2 - a^2)^2/2 - (b^4 - a^4)/4]}, \quad (4)$$

the volume ratio $\gamma = a^2/(b^2 - a^2)$ and Young's modulus ratio $\alpha = E_m/E_f$. σ_ℓ is the crack tip debond stress at the boundary between the bonded and debonded regions. If the interface is fully bonded, the above equations are still valid except for $\sigma_\ell = 0$ and $\ell = 0$. The corresponding solutions for the stress components in the debonded regions $-L \leq z \leq -(L-\ell)$ and $(L-\ell) \leq z \leq L$ are also given:

$$\sigma_f^z(z) = \frac{B_3}{B_2} [D_1 \exp(m_2 z) + D_2 \exp(m_1 z)] + \sigma_\ell [D_3 \exp(m_2 z) + D_4 \exp(m_1 z)] \quad (5)$$

$$\tau_1^{rz}(z) = -\frac{a}{2} \left\{ \frac{B_3}{B_2} [m_2 D_1 \exp(m_2 z) + m_1 D_2 \exp(m_1 z)] + \sigma_\ell [m_2 D_3 \exp(m_2 z) + m_1 D_4 \exp(m_1 z)] \right\} \quad (6)$$

where

$$B_3/B_2 = \frac{(1 + \gamma)\nu_m}{\alpha\nu_f + \gamma\nu_m} \sigma + \omega\bar{\sigma} \quad (7)$$

The details of parameters m_1 and m_2 which are a function of λ , and the non-dimensional coefficients D_1 , D_2 , D_3 and D_4 are given elsewhere [6]. The reciprocal length, λ , and the asymptotic debond stress, $\bar{\sigma}$, are related to the interface properties at the debonded interface, e.g. coefficient of friction, μ , and residual clamping stress, q_0 , as in the fibre pull-out model [7]:

$$\lambda = 2 \mu k / a \quad (8)$$

$$\bar{\sigma} = -q_0 / \omega k \quad (9)$$

where $\omega = \alpha\nu_f/(\alpha\nu_f + \gamma\nu_m)$ and $k = (\alpha\nu_f + \gamma\nu_m)/[\alpha(1 - \nu_f) + 1 + \nu_m + 2\gamma]$.

2.2 Criteria for Interface Debond and Fibre Fragmentation

Once the solutions for the stress components in the composite constituents are obtained for appropriate boundary conditions, the relevant criteria for interface debond and fibre fragmentation can be derived. Based on the shear strength debond criterion where the debond crack propagates when the maximum interfacial shear stress at the debond crack tip at $z = \pm(L-\ell)$ reaches the shear bond strength, τ_b , the external stress applied to the matrix, $\sigma = \sigma_{od}$, for debond crack propagation is derived:

$$\sigma_{od} = \frac{(2n_3/a\beta) \tau_b \coth[\beta(L-\ell)] - \alpha\nu_f(n_1 + \lambda)\bar{\sigma}}{(1+\gamma)[n_3/(\alpha+\gamma) + \nu_m n_1]} \quad (10)$$

where n_1 and n_3 are a complex function of the material and interface properties. When the applied stress is high enough to cause the maximum fibre axial stress to exceed the local fibre tensile strength, the fibre fractures. A fibre tensile strength model similar to that employed

previously [4] is used here to predict the average strength of the fibre, $\sigma_{TS}(2L_g)$, for a given gauge length, $2L_g$, based on the Weibull probability of failure:

$$\sigma_{TS}(2L_g) = [\sigma_u]^{-1/m} \Gamma(1 + 1/m) \quad (11)$$

where m and σ_u are the Weibull modulus and the scale factor, and Γ is the gamma function. Therefore, the average tensile strength of a fibre segment of length $2L$ is given by:

$$\sigma_{TS}(2L) = \sigma_{TS}(2L_g) [L/L_g]^{1/m} \quad (12)$$

Assuming the fibre always breaks at the centre where the axial stress is maximum, the external stress required for fibre fragmentation, $\sigma = \sigma_{of}$, is derived:

$$\sigma_{of} = \left(\frac{\alpha + \gamma}{1 + \gamma} \right) \sigma_{TS}(2L) \frac{\cosh[\beta(L-\ell)] - \sigma_\ell}{\cosh[\beta(L-\ell)] - 1} \quad (13)$$

Figure 2. Plot of interface shear bond strength, τ_b , versus fibre length, $2L$.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Specific results are calculated based on the solutions derived in the previous section for the model composite of carbon fibre and epoxy matrix for which the mechanical and interface properties are $E_f = 230$ GPa, $E_m = 3.0$ GPa, $\nu_f = 0.2$, $\nu_m = 0.4$, $\tau_b = 72.7$ MPa, $\mu = 1.5$ and $q_0 = -10$ MPa determined from the fibre pull-out test [7]. The Weibull statistics for the fibre tensile strength are $2L_g = 12$ mm, $\sigma_{TS}(2L_g) = 2.35$ GPa, $m = 3.8$, $\sigma_u = 5.0$ [6]. The conditions required to satisfy the three interface states (namely the full bonding, the partial debonding and the complete debonding or full frictional bonding) are also identified in terms of the relationship between the applied stress and the properties of the constituents and the interface. Finally, the fibre fragmentation criterion is applied to derive the mean fibre fragment length, $2L$, as a function of the applied stress for each interface state.

3.1 Full Bonding

For the interface to remain fully bonded during the fibre fragmentation process, the maximum interface shear stress obtained at the fibre ends has to be always smaller than τ_b :

$$\tau_b < \left(\frac{2}{a\beta}\right) \frac{\sinh(\beta L)}{\cosh(\beta L) - 1} \sigma_{TS}(2L) \quad (14)$$

Once the requirement for full bonding is satisfied, the mean fibre fragmentation length, $2L$, can be determined as a function of the external stress, σ_{of} , and the fibre tensile strength, $\sigma_{TS}(2L)$, by rearranging Equation (13) for $\sigma_\ell = 0$ and $\ell = 0$:

$$2L = \left(\frac{2}{\beta}\right) \cosh^{-1} \left\{ \frac{\sigma_{of}}{\sigma_{of} - [(\alpha + \gamma)/(1 + \gamma)]\sigma_{TS}(2L)} \right\} \quad (15)$$

Figure 3. Variation of mean fibre fragment length, $2L$, versus applied strain, predicted for the fully bonded interface.

The curve in Figure 2 plotted based on Equation (14) shows the critical combination of τ_b and the fibre length, $2L$, which allows initial debonding at the interface. Therefore, it is possible to evaluate the minimum fibre length, $(2L)_d$, under which fibre fragmentation takes place with the interface being fully bonded for a given value of τ_b (e.g. $(2L)_d = 2.71$ mm for $\tau_b = 72.7$ MPa). The plot given in Figure 3 indicates that the mean fibre fragment length decreases sharply within a small range of applied strain followed by an almost constant value with further increase in the applied strain. However, continuous fibre fracture into smaller segments whilst maintaining a fully bonded interface is limited by the imminent interfacial debonding at a large applied strain, as predicted by the curve shown in Figure 2. Therefore, unless τ_b is extremely large to prevent the interface from debonding, it is most unlikely that the fully bonded interface model can completely describe the relationship between mean fibre fragment length and applied strain in the fibre fragmentation test.

3.2 Partial Debonding

The stress distributions in the fibre and interface for the partially debonded interface are shown in Figure 4 where debond lengths are different for different τ_b values when the applied stress is constant $\sigma = 117.4$ MPa for a given fibre length $2L = 2$ mm. The fibre axial stresses are almost identical for these τ_b values, except near the boundary between the bonded and the debonded regions where the stresses are higher for a low τ_b . There is discontinuity of

interface shear stress at the boundary where the stress drop is large with a high τ_b . In the debonded region, the interface shear stress increases non-linearly towards the fibre ends due to the small Poisson contraction of the fibre compared to the matrix under uniaxial tension.

Figure 4. Distributions of (a) fibre axial stress and (b) interface shear stress along the fibre axis, z/a , at a given applied stress $\sigma = 117$ MPa for $\tau_b = 50$ MPa, 72.7 MPa and 100 MPa.

Since the crack tip debond stress, σ_ℓ , (and the debond length, ℓ) must be greater than zero for partial debonding at the interface, the condition for partial debonding becomes:

$$\sigma > \left(\frac{\alpha + \gamma}{1 + \gamma} \right) \left(\frac{2}{a\beta} \right) \tau_b \coth[\beta(L - \ell)] \tag{16}$$

Under this circumstance, whether debond continues or not depends strictly on the relative magnitude of the stresses required for debond propagation, σ_{od} , and for fibre fragmentation, σ_{of} , at a given debond length, ℓ . If σ_{od} is smaller than σ_{of} interfacial debonding continues in preference to fibre fragmentation; and conversely, if σ_{od} is greater than σ_{of} , then vice versa. The mean fibre fragmentation length, $2L$, which is the sum of the debonded and bonded lengths in the partial debond model, is determined from Equation (13):

$$2L = 2\ell + \frac{2}{\beta} \sinh^{-1} \left\{ \frac{(2\tau_b/a\beta)}{[(1+\gamma)/(\alpha+\gamma)]\sigma_{of} - \sigma_{TS}(2L)} \right\} \tag{17}$$

The applied stresses σ_{od} and σ_{of} plotted as a function of debond length, ℓ/a , in Figure 5 show that if the fibre is sufficiently long it fractures without debonding (because $\sigma_{od} > \sigma_{of}$) until its length reaches a characteristic value $(2L)_d$. Once debonding initiates it grows as the applied stress increases (and also the fibre fragmentation length decreases) as shown in Figure 6. It is certain that both the fibre length corresponding to initial debonding, $(2L)_d$, and the debond length at a given fibre length are greater for the interface with a low τ_b value. This is a direct result of the reduced stress required for debonding, σ_{od} , due to the low τ_b , whereas σ_{of} remains almost constant independent of τ_b . In addition to the maximum fibre length corresponding to debond initiation, a minimum fibre length is also identified below which no further debond propagates. This means that the partially debonded interface model is effective for the range of fibre lengths between these limits.

Figure 5 Plots of applied stresses required for interfacial debonding, σ_{od} , and for fibre fragmentation, σ_{of} , versus debond length, l/a .

Figure 6 Variation of debond length, $2l$, plotted as a function of mean fibre fragment length, $2L$, predicted for the partially debonded interface.

The mean fibre fragment length, which consists of bond length, $(2L-2l)$, and debond length, $2l$, is plotted versus applied strain in Figure 7. At a low strain the bond length component dominates, but as the applied strain increases the debond length component becomes increasingly more important, eventually the latter outdoing the former at a high strain. When the mean fibre fragment length is short at a large applied strain, an infinitesimal increase in debond length or further fibre fragmentation requires the applied stress to increase toward an infinite value. Therefore, a several-fold increase in applied stress at this stage would not cause any fibre fragmentation. In practice, the mean fibre fragment length obtained after substantial increases in load application without further fibre fragmentation is called the critical transfer length. Therefore, the shortest mean fibre fragment length determined at the end of the curve of Figure 7 can be regarded as the critical transfer length, $(2L)_c$, theoretically predicted for the model composite being considered.

Figure 7 Variation of mean fibre fragmentation length, $2L$, versus applied strain for $\tau_b = 72.7$ MPa for the partially debonded interface.

3.3 Complete Debonding (or Full Frictional Bonding)

For the completely debonded (or fully frictionally bonded) interface, the solutions for the stress components given in Equations (5) and (6) are still valid if the crack tip debond stress, σ_{ℓ} , is substituted by the fibre axial stress at the centre $\sigma_f^z(0)$ and $\ell = L$. $\sigma_f^z(0)$ for the frictional interface is determined for the boundary condition that the interface shear stress which is now controlled solely by the Coulomb friction law is minimum at the centre, i.e. $\tau_i^{rz}(0) = -\mu q_0$. The approximate solution for the mean fibre fragment length, $2L$, is also obtained:

$$2L = -\frac{2}{m_2} \ln \left\{ \frac{m_1(\alpha\nu_f + \gamma\nu_m) \sigma_{TS}(2L) + (\lambda - m_1)(\alpha\nu_f + \gamma\nu_m)\omega \bar{\sigma} - m_1\nu_m(1 + \gamma) \sigma_{of}}{- (m_1 - m_2)[(\alpha\nu_f + \gamma\nu_m)\omega \bar{\sigma} - \nu_m(1 + \gamma) \sigma_{of}]} \right\} \quad (18)$$

The mean fibre fragment length decreases with increasing applied strain as shown in Figure 8, similar to the fully bonded interface model. Several constant fibre tensile strengths are chosen for calculation to clearly show the general trend in a wide range of applied strains. It is noted that a high fibre tensile strength results in a high applied strain required to initiate the fibre fragmentation, though it does not affect much the mean fibre fragmentation length at a high applied strain.

Figure 8. Variation of mean fibre fragment length, $2L$, as a function of applied strain for the fully frictional interface for constant fibre tensile strengths $\sigma_{TS} = 6.0$ GPa, 8 GPa and 10 GPa.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

A major improvement of the present model relative to the earlier models [3,4] is that the conditions necessary to satisfy for the three interface states are quantitatively evaluated which allow the relationship between the mean fibre fragment length and the applied strain to be established during the whole fibre fragmentation process. Within the limitations of the present micromechanics analysis, the theoretical study for a model composite of carbon fibre-epoxy matrix clearly shows that while the fully bonded interface model can describe the fibre fragmentation process for low applied strains, the partially debonded interface model is most

suitable at the later stage for high applied strains. However, complete debonding is effectively discouraged due to the differential Poisson contraction between the fibre and matrix at the debonded interface. A non-zero critical value is reached for the mean fibre fragment length, consisting of the bonded and debonded lengths, when the applied strain required for further fibre fragmentation approaches infinity. The critical fibre length can be regarded as a material constant which is determined after substantial increment in the applied strain without further fibre fragmentation in experiment. In view of the co-existence of bonded and debonded regions comprising the critical transfer length, accurate measurements of both these lengths are necessary to properly characterise the relevant interface properties.

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